

AN AYURVEDIC REVIEW OF BALATISARA IN PAEDIATRIC AGE GROUP WITH EMPHASIS ON LODHRADI AND BALACHATURBHADRA CHURNA

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ABSTRACT

Balatisara is a common paediatric disorder described in Ayurveda, characterized by frequent passage of loose or watery stools due to impairment of digestive fire (*Agnimandya*) and vitiation of Doṣas. Children are particularly vulnerable because of their immature digestive and immune systems (*Aparipakva Agni*). Classical Ayurvedic texts emphasize *Ahara*, *Vihara*, and appropriate herbal formulations for effective management. Among various formulations, *Lodhradi Churna* and *Balachaturbhadrachurna* are frequently indicated in pediatric diarrheal disorders due to their *Dipana*, *Pachana*, *Grahi*, and *Stambhana* properties. This review aims to compile and critically analyse the Ayurvedic concept of *Balatisara*, its etiopathogenesis, clinical features, and therapeutic management, with special reference to these two classical

formulations. The study highlights their pharmacological attributes and therapeutic relevance in paediatric practice.

KEYWORDS: *Balatisara*, *Pediatric diarrhea*, *Agnimandya*, *Lodhradi Churna*, *Balachaturbhadrachurna*, Churna, Ayurveda.

INTRODUCTION

Balatisara, described extensively in Ayurvedic classics, is a significant cause of morbidity in children. Ayurveda considers childhood (*Balya Avastha*) as *Kapha*-dominant with underdeveloped digestive capacity, making children prone to gastrointestinal disorders.^[1] Improper feeding practices, unhygienic food, and infections contribute to the manifestation of *Atisara* in children. Ayurveda emphasizes correction of *Agni*, elimination of *Ama*, and restoration of gut function rather than mere symptomatic control.^[2] Classical formulations such as *Lodhradi Churna* (described in *yogratnakara*) and *Balachaturbhadra Churna* (mentioned in *Bhaisajya ratnavali*) are traditionally used in paediatric *Atisara* due to their safety and efficacy.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

Aim

To review the Ayurvedic concept of *Balatisara* in children and evaluate the therapeutic role of *Lodhradi Churna* and *Balachaturbhadra Churna*.

Objectives

1. To describe the etiopathogenesis of *Balatisara* from an Ayurvedic perspective
2. To compile classical references related to *Balatisara*
3. To review the composition and properties of *Lodhradi* and *Balachaturbhadra Churna*
4. To analyse their role in paediatric diarrhoea management.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This is a conceptual review study based on:

- Classical Ayurvedic texts such as *Charaka Samhita*, *Sushruta Samhita* and *Ashtanga Samgraha*.
- Classical formulation texts including *Yogaratanakara* and *Bhaisajya Ratnavali*
- Published research articles and pediatric diarrhea guidelines
- Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India

Relevant verses and therapeutic principles were critically analyzed.

REVIEW / RESULTS

Atisara is defined as frequent passage of watery stools due to vitiation of *Doṣas* and derangement of *Agni*.^[3] In children, it is termed *Balatisara*, influenced by weak digestion and

improper feeding. the Nidana (Etiological Factors) of *balatisara* are: Intake of heavy, cold, or incompatible foods, Overfeeding or improper breastfeeding, Contaminated food and water, Teething period and infections, Suppression of natural urges^[4] The Samprapti (Pathogenesis) can be explained as follows:

Nidana → *Agnimandya* → *Ama formation* → Dosh vitiation (*Kapha-predominant*) → *Rasavaha Srotodushti* → Frequent loose stools.^[5] The *Lakshana* (Clinical Features) of *balatisara* are: Loose or watery stools, Loss of appetite (*Aruchi*), Abdominal discomfort, Weakness and dehydration, Coated tongue.^[6]

Therapeutic Management in Ayurveda

General Principles

- *Ama Pachcana*
- *Agni Dipana*
- *Grahi* and *Stambhana* therapy
- Use of mild, child-friendly formulations^[7]

Lodhradi Churna is Mentioned in Yogaratnakara – *Atisara Chikitsa*. It is *Kashaya, Katu* in rasa and *laghu, ruksha* in Guna Its Karma are *Grahi, Stambhana, Dipana*^[8] It Controls stool frequency, improves digestion, and strengthens intestinal mucosa, making it suitable for *Balatisara*.

Ingredients and its role in Balatisara

Lodhra (*Symplocos racemosa*): The *Kashaya* rasa and *Ruksha guna* of *Lodhra* help in absorbing excess intestinal fluid and checking bowel hypermotility, thereby reducing stool frequency. Its *Grahi* and *Stambhana* actions strengthen intestinal mucosa and prevent dehydration, making it highly beneficial in paediatric diarrhea where fluid loss is predominant.

Pippali (*Piper longum*): It corrects *Agnimandya*, the primary cause of *Balatisara*. Its *Dipana– Pachana* action helps digest *Ama*, while *Madhura Vipaka* ensures nourishment without aggravating *Pitta*, making it safe for children. It also supports gut immunity and prevents recurrence.

Sugandhabala (*Pavonia odorata*): It alleviates abdominal pain, distension, and discomfort associated with *Atisara*. Its *Vatanulomana* property helps normalise intestinal movement,

while *Dipana* action aids digestion, particularly useful in colicky diarrhoea.

Balachaturbhadra Churna

It is Described in Bhaisajya Ratnavali– Balroga Adhikara it is *Dipana-Pachana, grahi*, antimicrobial and Has imodulatory actions.^[9] It is Especially effective in infectious and *Amaja Atisara* in children.

Ingredients

Mustaka (*Cyperus rotundus*). Mustaka is one of the best Grahi drugs described in Ayurveda. It corrects digestive impairment, reduces intestinal secretion, and is especially useful in *Āmaj* and infectious diarrhea commonly seen in children.

Pippali (*Piper longum*). Acts as a bioavailability enhancer (*Yogavahi*), improving the efficacy of other drugs in the formulation. It maintains Agni and prevents post-diarrheal indigestion.

Ativisha (*Aconitum heterophyllum*). Ativisha is a drug of choice in paediatric disorders. It effectively digests Ama, controls fever-associated diarrhoea, and prevents complications. Its safety and efficacy in children are well emphasised in classical texts.

Karkatshringi (*Pistacia integerrima*). *Karkatshringi* strengthens intestinal tone, reduces mucus secretion, and supports recovery from weakness. It is particularly helpful in chronic or recurrent *Balatisara*.

DISCUSSION

Balatisara reflects a state of impaired digestion and disturbed intestinal function. Both *Lodhradi* and *Balachaturbhadra Churna* act by correcting *Agni*, digesting *ama* and stabilizing bowel movements. Their ingredients possess documented antimicrobial, anti-diarrheal, and digestive properties, aligning with modern concepts of paediatric diarrhoea management.^[10–12]

CONCLUSION

Balatisara is a significant paediatric disorder effectively explained and managed through Ayurvedic principles. *Lodhradi Churna* and *Balachaturbhadra Churna* are classical, safe, and effective formulations that address the root cause of the disease. Their judicious use along with dietary regulation can provide holistic management of paediatric diarrhoea.

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